

D8.2 Ethics Management Plan

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BEYOND Consortium

	ROLE	NAME	Acronym	Country
1.	Coordinator	University of Oslo	UiO	Norway
2.	Partner	European Network of Research Ethics Committees	EUREC	Belgium
3.	Partner	High Council For The Evaluation of Research and Higher Education	HCERES	France
4.	Partner	French Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment	INRAE	France

5.	Partner	Oslo Metropolitan University	OsloMet	Norway
6.	Partner	Eurosis Federation of Finnish Learned Societies	TSV	Finland
7.	Partner	University of Central Lancashire-Cyprus	UCLanCY	Cyprus
8.	Partner	University of Helsinki	UH	Finland
9.	Partner	University of Humanistic Studies	UHS	The Netherlands
10.	Partner	University of Latvia	UL	Latvia
11.	Partner	University of Tartu	UTARTU	Estonia
12.	Partner	Stichting VUMC / The Embassy of Good Science	VUMC	The Netherlands
13.	AP	Trilateral Research LTD	TRI	UK
14.	AP	Heriot-Watt University	HWU	SCT

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1. Tasks of the BEYOND project and ethics oversight

The BEYOND project consists of the following Work Packages (WPs) and tasks:

	YEAR 1				YEAR 2				YEAR 3			
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
WP1 Literature review & monitoring of cases (EXPLORE)												
1.1 Literature review												
1.2 Monitoring and reviews of cases												
1.3. Systematic review of validated RM instruments												
1.4 Socio-economic consequences of RM												
WP 2 Public consultation and stakeholder engagement (ENGAGE)												
2.1 Planning of the consultation												
2.2 Mapping of stakeholders												
2.3 Organizing consultations												
2.4 Qualitative and quantitative analysis												
2.5 Co-creation of manual and guidelines												
WP3 Developing behavioural interventions towards ethical research (EXPLORE & GUIDE)												
3.1 Framework of QRPs												
3.2 Contextual interventions to combat RM												
3.3 Creating and validating vignettes												
3.4 Testing contextual features & interventions												
WP 4 Methodologies to measure effects of ethics and integrity training (EXPLORE & GUIDE)												
4.1. Exploration of measurement features												
4.2. Assessment of affordances and constraints												
4.3. Development of measurements												
WP5 Best practices manual, guidelines to supplement SOPs, & roadmap (GUIDE & EQUIP)												
5.1 Guideline/manual/roadmap scoping												
5.2 Scoping review of existing RE/RI guidelines												
5.3 Formulation and reformulation of questions												
5.4 Evidence synthesis												
5.5 Drafting of guidelines												
5.6 Drafting of the Best Practices Manual												
5.7 Development of the 2030 Roadmap												
WP 6 RE/RI training and education (EQUIP)												
6.1 Map existing training materials and tools												
6.2 Devise a trainer guide												
6.3 Develop new training materials												
6.4 Pilot-test and evaluate training materials and tools												
WP 7 Horizontal coordination, dissemination, exploitation, and communication (ENGAGE)												
7.1 DEC plan												
7.2. Horizontal coordination												
7.3. Communication Actions												
7.4. Dissemination and exploitation												
WP 8 Project management												
8.1 Scientific project coordination												
8.2 Project management												
8.3 Financial management												
8.4 Data Management Plan												
8.5 Ethics and risk management												
8.6 Management of Stakeholder Advisory Board												

Most of the WPs, except for WP8, will do research, and in several of the WPs, research participants will be involved, stakeholders will be consulted, and personal data will be processed. This document outlines how the project ensures the highest ethical standards of research will be maintained and upheld.

The project will, in all instances, comply fully with standard research ethics principles and only collect data with the required ethics approvals (for the interventional studies) and the informed consent of the participating stakeholders (for all studies requiring research participants). Benefit-sharing, in the form of sharing research products, is intrinsic in the project as all deliverables will be made available open-access.

All potential participants are non-vulnerable adults with full capacity to consent. The data will be archived by the responsible partner institutions based on their SOPs. Unless restricted by privacy and confidentiality considerations and GDPR requirements, data will also be published in FAIR data repositories, such as Zenodo. A detailed description of data protection and sharing is outlined in D8.1: Data Management Plan.

The processing of the collected personal data will comply fully with the General Data Protection Regulation (<https://gdpr-info.eu>), and pertinent national data protection law.

2. Ethics Approvals

The BEYOND project collects and processes personal research data from interventional studies, observational studies, stakeholder meetings and consultations. WPs 3 and 4 will both hold interventional studies, while WPs 1, 2, 5, and 6 require literature reviews, observational research methods (requiring interviews, focus group discussions), and other engagement events with stakeholders.

While observational studies do not require ethics approval, though Norway requires notification of observational studies, interventional studies to require ethics approval. Procedures and requirements may differ among the Member States. Stakeholder consultations and studies that do not require the inclusion and/or the processing of human data do not usually require any kind of ethics approval in several EU Member States, though there could be differences in terms of ethics oversight regulations and requirements per Member State. *In all instances, ethics oversight regulations in the responsible partner's/partners' national regulations (i.e., the country of the data controller) will be followed.*

WPs 3 and 4 will facilitate interventional studies requiring human participants. In both cases, the WP leads (i.e., the University of Tartu and the University of Helsinki, respectively) will be responsible for securing the required research ethics committee approvals.

All studies requiring ethics approval or notification will only commence after the required approvals have been received from the responsible partner's (i.e., the partner considered the data controller) country.

3. Informed consent and data storage

Participants in the interventional and observational studies, as well as those involved in engagement events, will be provided with participant information materials prior to their participation, and will be asked to give explicit consent to participation and data collection.

The participant information materials and consent forms will be produced by the partner responsible for the specific data collection. The participant information materials and informed consent forms will be based on the partner's local templates and follow the partner's Member State requirements and institutional SOPs in terms of storage of data. For the partner institutions concerned, they will take appropriate measures in handling, receiving, and storing the signed informed consent forms in accordance with the Member State's regulations. For both data and informed consent, if practicable and necessary, the responsible partner institution, with the Coordinating institution, the University of Oslo, will be specified as joint Data Controllers for specific activities of the project. Otherwise, the responsible partner institution will be the sole Data Controller.

More specifically the participant information materials will contain information about the following, as well as other information required by the national authorities, as specified in the 2013 version of the Declaration of Helsinki (DoH):

- aims,
- methods,
- sources of funding,
- any possible conflicts of interest,
- institutional affiliations of the researcher,
- the anticipated benefits and potential risks of the study and the discomfort it may entail,
- post-study provisions and any other relevant aspects of the study.
- the right to refuse to participate in the study or to withdraw consent to participate at any time without reprisal. (Association, 2013)
- data will be securely and confidentially stored in a GDPR-compliant storage solution until 5 years after the project.

In all instances, attention will be "given to the specific information needs of individual potential subjects as well as to the methods used to deliver the information" (Association, 2013)

On top of these requirements specified by the DoH, the participants will also be informed of the following:

- the activities involved in participation,
- Data Protection Information, including specification of the types of personal data being collected and processed, the anonymization procedures, and final deposit in data repository (if relevant),
- confidentiality,

- contact details of researchers,
- contact details for complaints.

4. Data Storage

Work packages	Data storage	Data retention timeline	Record destruction
WP1	<p>All digital data will be stored on secure and password-protected servers of Trilateral Research or Oslo University or on a password-protected hard drive.</p> <p>Signed consent forms for interviews in paper form will be kept in a locked file cabinet at Trilateral Research's UK office</p>	<p>Anonymous data from public consultation will be stored without time limit.</p> <p>Interview transcripts will be stored for 5 years after the end of the project.</p>	<p>Interview/focus group recordings and transcripts will be destroyed 5 years after the end of the project.</p>
WP2	<p>All digital data will be stored on secure and password-protected servers of University of</p>	<p>Anonymous data from public consultation will be stored without time limit.</p>	<p>Interview recordings will be destroyed</p>

	<p>Latvia compliant with the GDPR or on a password-protected hard drive.</p> <p>Signed consent forms for interviews in paper form will be kept in a locked file cabinet.</p>	<p>Interview transcripts will be stored for 5 years after the end of the project.</p>	<p>after transcription.</p> <p>Interview transcripts will be destroyed 5 years after the end of the project.</p>
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WP3	All data and materials will be stored on secure and passwordprotected servers of University of Tartu compliant with the GDPR.	Anonymous data will be stored without time limit.	
WP4	<p>Signed consent forms on paper will be kept in a locked locker in an office which is locked in a building that requires a clearance pass to enter and move between building sections</p> <p>Electronic materials we have Redcap and a local secured folder, Zfolder, at the University of Helsinki</p>	Within the project time	Anonymised materials deleted five years after project ends.
WP5	Signed consent forms as well as non-anonymized data will be kept in UiO's secure servers, specifically utilizing the Services for Sensitive Data and will be kept up to 1 year after the project.	Anonymized data will be stored without limit.	Stakeholder consultation transcripts will be destroyed after transcription. Anonymized data will be deleted a year
			after the project.

WP6	All data and materials will be stored on secure and passwordprotected servers of EUREC Office compliant with the GDPR.	5 years after the end of the study	All recordings will be destroyed after transcription and the transcripts kept for 5 years after the end of the study
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5. Data protection and anonymization

BEYOND will process personal data quantitatively and qualitatively. In some instances, transcriptions will be necessary. Data will be anonymized unless participants consented otherwise, and public consultation events will be guided by ethical rules (as stipulated in research ethics guidelines and other related principles such as the Chatham House Rule) and trust. In the case of transcription of audio and video files that require anonymization, after verification of transcription the audio and video files will be deleted.

The project will not maintain a link between the anonymized data and the identifying data of the participants. All data analysis will be performed using the anonymized data, and only anonymized data will be deposited in data repositories at the end of the project (see also D8.1, Data Management Plan). Research participants will be asked to provide explicit consent to deposition in a data repository as part of the informed consent process prior to data collection.

6. Sharing of results

Research results will all be shared via open access, may it be in the form of publications, training materials, popular science literature, or through open data.

7. Reference

World Medical Association (2013). *Declaration of Helsinki - ethical principles for medical research involving human subjects*. <http://www.wma.net/en/30publications/10policies/b3/>